

Time-Frequency Analysis on Exchange Rate Indicators

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Abstract

Studying periods of cyclical components in any time series data presents an important part of the overall series information. Spectral components provide information of the period but lack the capability of placing them in time. Time-frequency analysis provides integrated information about period's length and time allocation within any selected signal. In order to obtain the most appropriate analytical signal or isolation of a detrended component of the original signal, applications of filters with a combination of characteristic functions are used. This study analyzes data pre-processing techniques and its implication on the cyclical component (ϵ_t). The analytical part is isolated on which the application of selected bilinear time-frequency distributions is applied for extracting or detecting the length of a period within a composed exchange rate signal.

1 Introduction

Exchange rate formation present one of the key tools of the financial system. In its foundational construction, they determine the evolution of the monetary system. They provide trading decision mechanisms within any sector and are the bases of integrated trading platforms (Reuters, Datastream, Forex, Bloomberg,...). Asset prices of commodities, company's liabilities and traded volumes are tightly linked to the exchange rate and money reserves in specific countries. Investors are not only interested in the current rate, but a method on how to minimize risk and hedge future investments, speculating the error margin of the future rate. Therefore, reliance on derivatives products, mainly currency options are of great interest in this study. One of the possibility for reliable hedging strategy when investing in foreign assets is the estimation of the future trading and rate interval of currency derivatives products.

Adequate analysis of exchange rate signals is necessary to provide meaningful solutions to a selected currency forecast and the status of market development. This paper will analyze periodicity within an exchange rate product using a variety of filtering techniques to determine periods and lengths within selected signals. The periodicity is linked to the asset being traded and the number of transactions executed on the specific element. The analyzed element is not the underlying asses but a combination of traded volume and rate differential of

the instrument that evolves through time. Therefore, the exchange rate period of main currencies that constitute the SDR structure and the SDR signal itself could be a significant contributor to the understanding of the overall market cycle and the determinant factor of subsequent evolution of currency derivatives, and the number of traded assets, especially options.

The real exchange rate is the level of a relative price of one country's goods in terms of another's; the real exchange rate differential is quoted as a ratio and is essentially a rate of change or commonly known tool to remove seasonality. In essence, of interest are rate differential and its adjacent volume turnover data. Exchange rate theories combine the uncovered interest parity relationship with the assumption that the real exchange rate deviates from its long run level only temporarily. Under these assumptions, shocks to the real exchange rate - which are often viewed as caused by shocks to monetary policy - are expected to reverse themselves over time [15]. Major central banks in continental regions have the potential to intervene on foreign exchange markets. Intervention operations, even though rare, are effected solely through foreign reserves held by central banks. Taking the European Central Bank (ECB) as an example, it independently can operate in currencies of countries outside the euro area's exchange rate policy. The ECB council may act unanimously to conclude formal agreements in the exchange rate system for the euro vis-a-vis currencies outside the EU. However, institutional measures always have to respect the primary objective of the monetary system, which is price stability. To effectively conduct the monetary policy, the exchange rate should be seen as the combined outcome of both economic development and economic policies, rather than as an independent objective.

In order to guarantee intervention at any point in time, a central bank holds a predefined amount of liquid resources sufficient for any foreign exchange intervention. Liquidity and security are the basic requirements for the investment of foreign reserves. Central banks have a strategic and tactical investment framework, including currency distribution, trade off between interest rate risk and return, and credit risk and liquidity requirements. Investment of foreign reserves lacks transparency exposure due to unwarranted impact on financial markets. Foreign exchange rate operations with foreign reserves ensure consistency with the single monetary and exchange rate policy. More specifically, it applies to transactions that have a potential to affect the exchange rate or domestic liquidity conditions. However, investment operations in foreign financial markets do not affect a single monetary and exchange rate policy of the ECB [15].

National amount outstanding options of global OTC (over-the counter and excluding organized exchanges) within the second half of 2010 was recorded at 10,092 billions US dollars (representing roughly 2% of all OTC contracts and 17% of all Foreign exchange contracts) as reported by The Bank for International Settlements.

2 Data Processing

2.1 Signal Definition

Let $p(s)_t$ represent a time signal of any exchange rate and let $v(s)_t$ represent the volume quantity traded in a given day t . Then, to determine the impact of price or volume development, one of the parameters is fixed for both periods, therefore we obtain Laspeyers index for a composition of elements in two forms:

$$P(x)_t = \frac{p(s)_t v(s)_t}{p(s)_{t-1} v(s)_t}, \quad (1)$$

$$Q(x)_t = \frac{p(s)_t v(s)_t}{p(s)_t v(s)_{t-1}}, \quad (2)$$

With finalized signal definition at time t

$$S(x)_t = P(s)_t \cdot Q(s)_t. \quad (3)$$

More on the nuber theory development and details on the Laplayers index can be found in [8].

2.2 Filtering Techniques

2.2.1 Median Filter

Median is used for measuring a central tendency in a chosen signal and is more robust to extreme values and outliers then method of evaluating simple arithmetical mean. The median value is evaluated with:

$$s_i = (s_{i+1} - s_{i-1}) \frac{t_i - t_{i-1}}{t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}} + s_{i-1}. \quad (4)$$

In this study, to obtain the proper analytical signal, the length of the filtering window is adjusted. As the number of elements in the analytical window increases, the trend line converges to the actual median value of the series. Median filter is problematic when evaluating its values at the tails of the series. In this case, the extreme value adjustment was solved with retaining the length of the filtering window and populated it with values identical to the last (or first) value of the series, but other more representative techniques may apply.

2.2.2 Hodrick-Prescott Filter

Hodrick-Prescott (HP) filter [7] splits a signal s_t into a growth (or trend) component g_t and a cyclical component c_t . Therefore, the signal becomes a composition $s_t = g_t + c_t$. With the HP filter for an evaluation of the growth component, the algorithm minimizes the difference between a signal and trend values g_1, \dots, g_T :

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{g_1, \dots, g_T} = \sum_{t=1}^T [s_n - g_n] + \lambda \sum_{t=1}^T [(g_{t+1} - g_t) - (g_n - g_{n-1})]^2, \quad (5)$$

where λ is a smoothing parameter and T the length of a signal. If $\lambda = 0$, filter does not exhibit any smoothing. In case when $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, the smoothed signal converges to a linear trend. Adequate value selection for λ are:

- 100 for detecting annual periods,
- 1600 for detecting quarterly periods,
- 14400 for detecting monthly periods.

2.3 Filter with Characteristic Functions

The filter with characteristic functions (CF) in the filtering window adopts to different window length and uses specifically derived CF on each length of the window and adjusts for each data point. The error term ϵ is deduced for each case separately with the window moving at the speed $t+1$. A characteristic function is estimated with the least squared method. For the general case we obtain:

$$y(s) = p_1 s_n + p_2 s_{n-1} + \dots + p_n s + p_{n+} \quad (6)$$

2.4 Filter with Normalized Windows

Filter with normalized windows standardizes analytical segment with:

$\mu = E(S)$ and $\sigma = \sqrt{E[(S - \mu)^2]}$, where:

$$Z_t = \frac{S_t - \mu}{\sigma}.$$

3 Time-Frequency Analysis

A sequence of consequently measured variables is normally called a *time series*, however, this work refers to it as a *discrete signal in time* or shortly *signal*. Such measures can be analyzed in the time domain, frequency domain or in a time-frequency domain.

Time domain $[s(t)]$ provides information about a time evolution of a signal, frequency domain $[s(f)]$ or *the spectrum* provides information about signal's periodicity and the time-frequency domain $[s(t, f)]$ joins time and frequency information into a common domain.

Time-frequency representations (TFR) are most useful when analyzing non-stationary signals or when length of the periods remain equal, but their amplitude is effected. Such representations are classified in two groups, linear or atomic distributions and bilinear or quadratic distributions. Bilinear processing is further split into the Cohen and affine class. To provide a thoughtful comparison between Cohen class distributions a construction of two synthesized signals is necessary. To define an exchange rate cycle definition the example should emerge from predefined periods and amplitudes in the constructed signal.

3.1 Signal Definition

To represent time-frequency analysis, a simple synthesized signal and a synthesized signal with changing amplitude are constructed. Such signals are used to verify outcomes from time-frequency distributions.

Theoretical explanation of time-frequency distributions pertinent to the exchange rate signals use two different sinusoidal signals. First, *simple synthesized signal* entails of a sum of three sinusoidal functions with constant period and amplitude. The second signal, *synthesized signal with a change in amplitude*, is a composition of three sinusoidal functions that change over time. However, a random component can be added to an oscillating synthesized signal.

Definition 1 Let a_i be an amplitude of a signal and ω the period of a signal, where $\omega = \frac{2\pi}{P}$, therefore:

$$S_{BCE}(t) = a_1 \sin(\omega_1 t) + a_2 \sin(\omega_2 t) + a_3 \sin(\omega_3 t), \quad (7)$$

$$S_{BCC} = \begin{cases} a_1 \sin(\omega_1 t) + a_2 \sin(\omega_2 t) + a_3 \sin(\omega_3 t); & 0 \leq t \leq \frac{T}{2}, \\ a_4 \sin(\omega_1 t) + a_5 \sin(\omega_2 t) + a_6 \sin(\omega_3 t); & \frac{T}{2} \leq t \leq T. \end{cases}$$

Both signals contain predefined periods and amplitudes that correspond to a specific cycle in the evolution of the exchange rate signal. Predefined quantities are provided in table 1 and pair with expected cycles in the exchange rate signal.

Table 1: Theoretical cycles - predetermined phases and amplitudes.

	Simple		Composed		
	$\omega(days)$	a_i	$\omega(days)$	$a_i; t < \frac{T}{2}$	$a_i; t > \frac{T}{2}$
P_1	260	0.3	260	0.3	0.05
P_2	65	0.09	65	0.09	0.09
P_3	30	0.18	30	0.18	0.3

3.2 Signal Conversion

The most common tool to convert a time signal in its frequency domain is called a Fourier Transformation. Frequency analysis provides information about signal's periodicity.

Fourier transform \mathcal{F} of an aperiodical signal $s(t)$ and the inverse Fourier transform \mathcal{F}^{-1} are defined as:

$$F(\omega) = \mathcal{F}(s(t)) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s(t)e^{-j\omega t} dt, \quad (8)$$

$$s(t) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}(F(\omega)) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(\omega)e^{j\omega t} d\omega. \quad (9)$$

In the case of a periodic function, a signal can be written as with a Fourier series:

$$\overline{s(t)} = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(n)e^{jn\omega t}, \quad (10)$$

$$F(n) = \frac{1}{T} \int_t^{t+T} s(t)e^{-jn\omega t} dt, \quad (11)$$

where $\omega = \frac{2\pi}{T}$, T is a period of a function, and $F(\omega)$ a Fourier transformation at frequency ω in $j = \sqrt{-1}$. Since $F(\omega)$ is generally a complex function, it can be defined as $F(\omega) = |F(\omega)|e^{j\Theta(\omega)}$, where $|F(\omega)|$ is the amplitude spectrum and $\Theta(\omega)$ a phase spectrum, $|F(\omega)|^2$ represents a force spectrum.

There exists a drawback in applying a Fourier transform to either a signal or signal's autocorrelation function. If signal's statistical properties change over time within a time and frequency domain, a Fourier transform loses time information about a spectral instances in the evolving signal. Hence, providing a justifiable reason to observe a selected signal's evolution in a time-frequency domain.

3.3 Bilinear (quadratic) Time-Frequency Analysis

Time-frequency representations are provided in the 2D space as a pair (t, f) . Such distributions are mappings of any signal into a TF domain:

$$\tau : s(t) \rightarrow T_s(t, f).$$

For a simple characterization of a signal in time and frequency domain it is wise to consider the average localization and dispersion of a selected distribution. Considering instantaneous energy $|s(t)|^2$ in $|S(f)|^2$ as probability distributions average localization and dispersion relate to average time and frequency in terms of average value and variance. Where E_s is the terminating energy of a signal:

$$E_s = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |s(t)|^2 dt < \infty. \quad (12)$$

Table 2: Average localization and dispersion.

Quantity	Formula
average time	$t_m = \frac{1}{E_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t s(t) ^2 dt$
average frequency	$f_m = \frac{1}{E_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f S(f) ^2 df$
time variance	$T^2 = \frac{4\pi}{E_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (t - t_m)^2 s(t) ^2 dt$
frequency variance	$B^2 = \frac{4\pi}{E_s} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f - f_m)^2 S(f) ^2 df$

Functions $|s(t)|^2$ and $|S(f)|^2$ are considered as energy distributions in time and frequency. In a similar manner, the energy distributions of time and frequency or $\rho_s(t, f)$ is defined as:

$$E_s = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho_s(t, f) dt df. \quad (13)$$

Generally, the energy of a signal is defined as a quadratic distribution. From equations (12) and (13) it is clearly seen that energy distribution satisfies partial properties:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho_s(t, f) dt = |S(f)|^2, \quad (14)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho_s(t, f) df = |s(t)|^2, \quad (15)$$

If a signal is presented in a time-frequency domain, localization of average quantities (t_m, f_m) and dispersion of a standard deviation be defined in both domains (T for time and B for frequency domain).

A product $T \times B$ when considering the *Cauchy-Schwarz inequality* in the definition (12), it is possible to prove:

$$T \times B \geq 1. \quad (16)$$

In other words, when limiting the product in (16) the lower bound of signal's energy distribution resolution is given with a time-frequency domain. Therefore, it is impossible to simultaneously obtain high time and frequency resolution. Such property is called *Heisenberg-Gabor principle* and it is applied when considering a decision about adequate analytical window's size.

Analytical Signal

In the example of a real signal the energy of a spectral density function $|S(f)|^2$ is symmetric to a frequency function f , where property $S(-f) = S(f)$ holds.¹ A real signal $s(t)$ is described with the *Hilbert transform*.²

A real signal $s(t)$ is connected with the value of a complex signal $s_a(t)$ defined as:

$$s_a(t) = s(t) + jHT(s(t)), \quad (17)$$

where $HT(s(t))$ is a Hilbert transform of the signal s ; $s_a(t)$ is an analytical signal associated with the real signal $s(t)$. Signal $s_a(t)$ is analytical because it satisfies *Cauchy-Reimann* properties:

$$S_a = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } f < 0 \\ S(0) & \text{for } f = 0 \\ 2(S(f)) & \text{for } f > 0. \end{cases}$$

Analytical signal $s_a(t)$ removes negative frequency values and positive values are doubled.

¹The average value of the frequency f always equals 0.

²This methodology removes inadequate symmetry properties.

3.3.1 Cycles in a Time-Frequency Domain

A thoughtful comparison about bilinear time-frequency adequacy on synthesized signals can be found in [10]. The theoretical explanation of a cycle deduction is presented through the two synthesized signals with predefined periods and amplitudes.

Time-frequency figures provide information about the size of the signal's energy distribution in the time-frequency domain. Such information is about signals's properties. Graphical time-frequency representations are 3D functions that can be presented in the 3 dimensional plane or as a projection of the 3 dimensional plane into a 2 dimensional plane with different methods.

In this context or for the purposes of the subsequent analysis, 2D graphical representations are used to depict signal's energy with a color scheme. A 2-dimensional representation allows for shift in distributions, however, in this manner the process creates additional interpretation problems in conjunction with the color scheme.

The images on its x-axes present time (in days). Frequency scale provides values of a normalized frequency f . Normalized frequency is defined as a ratio of sampling frequency fv . For the purposes of this discussion $fv = \text{day}^{-1}$. When looking for a period in *days* a normalized frequency is defined as $\frac{1}{fv}$ days.

Spectrogram

Spectrogram is a time-frequency distribution belonging to the energy distributions and is most widely used energy distribution for speech signal representation in a time-frequency domain. Spectrogram is calculated as a short-time power spectrum of a signal $s(t)$ and multiplied with a windowing function $h(t)$:

$$S_s(t, f) = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s(u)h(u - t)e^{-j2\pi fu} du \right|^2. \quad (18)$$

Spectrogram presents a real valued nonnegative energy distributions. With $S_s(t, f)$ it is possible to observe an energy of a signal in a time-frequency domain centered at the point (t, f) .³

To observe periodicity in a time-frequency domain with this distribution, both synthesized signals are observed. Graphical representations presented in 1 show the energy distribution jointly for both signals. In figure 1a the energy distributes on three different values of normalized frequencies and is continuous throughout the whole period. The image 1b clearly acknowledge the change in amplitude, however the period and its length remain constant.

³For all Spectrogram properties see [1]

Figure 1: Spectrogram of a simple synthesized signal and a synthesized signal with different amplitudes.

Page Distribution

If energy representation is defined as:

$$E_s(t, f) = \left| \int_{-\infty}^t s(u) e^{-j2\pi f u} du \right|^2,$$

allows to derive a *Page distribution* as a cumulative energy distribution and its quantity is a derivative of spectral density's energy, then it holds:

$$P_s(t, f) = \frac{d}{dt} E_s(t, f) = 2\Re\{s(t) \left(\int_{-\infty}^t s(u) e^{-j2\pi f u} du \right)^* e^{-j2\pi f t}\}. \quad (19)$$

Page distribution is a member of Cohen's class and its thoughtful description and derivation can be found in [1]. Page distribution in [10] and [14] was shown to be the most effective tool in determining periodicity in aggregated index structures when applying the Hodrick-Preescot filter to the original signal.

Figure 2 shows energy distribution in time-frequency domain obtained with a Page distribution of both synthesized signals. Its periodicity detection efficacy can be observed in many ways. In figure 2a the energy distribution adequately detects periods, their length and amplitude. Figure 2b shows an improvement from the spectrogram distribution, because it also adequately detects a change in amplitude within all values of the assigned normalized frequency values and transcribes the length of the period with a lower amplitude when $t > \frac{T}{2}$.

Figure 2: Page distribution of a simple synthesized signal and a synthesized signal with different amplitudes.

4 Time-Frequency Analysis on Selected Indicators

Empirical part of this study includes a combination of filters to adequately produce an efficient aggregate indicator of volume and rates traded in this case on the Forex platform of over-the-counter currencies. Several combinations of filters and time-frequency distributions are used to observe the expected cycles within the constructed exchange rate signals, combining data from closing historical rates and volume turnover information on currencies that constitute the main global currency, the SDR. Information about price and volume are combined as a percent change differential described in section 2. In this manner, outliers are easily identified and the analytical component combines more information to observe the true cycle between exchange rates and trading volume. If the value increase differential at time i is significantly higher from the differential at time $i + 1$, then the combined signal does not provide meaningful information. High volume volatility showed to be the problem in this particular case when observing the combined signals. At specific times, the traded volume on specific dates provided a useless signal (non-representative cyclical component) for further investigations. High jumps in volume occurred on random instances throughout the lifetime of the signal, however, world events or significant fiscal or monetary policy oriented decisions should be carefully considered with the conjunction of significantly higher volume of traded instruments in the market. Such problem was detected in both analyzed signals, the EUR/USD rate and USD/JPY rate. Other currencies were not considered at this time. Selected exchange rates of USD/EUR and USD/JPY for this study were obtained from the Forex trading platform. The rate itself does not exhibit significant jumps as its associated volume data. Data can be obtained free of charge when a person creates a demo trading account.

An additional outstanding value check was conducted when outliers were obtained if specific value was at most 2 standard deviations away from the average value. In both cases, the reduction of outstanding values in volume data did not improve the analysis or provide a meaningful signal on which possibly periodical cycles of combined rate and volume signal could be observed. Such methodology should not be rejected on all instruments, but definitely on the exchange rate derivatives traded on unregulated OTC markets (the Forex platform).

4.1 Exchange Rate Signal

The exchange rate signal of both currencies is observed in the time-frequency domain after multiple data pre-processing techniques. In both cases, a HP, median, polynomial, and standardized filters are applied to obtain a desired cyclical component.

Same filtering properties were applied to both exchange rate signals. In the case of a Hodrick-Prescott, value of the smoothing parameter λ was set to 128,000 and in the case of a median filter, the length of an analytical window was set to 250 trading days. Both cyclical components were observed with Spectrogram and Page distribution in the time-frequency domain. Even though observed currencies are the driving forces of two continents with different trading habits and volumes, similar cyclical behavior should be observed due to:

- elements of a SDR structure,
- relation to London's 4 PM fix.

USD/EUR Exchange Rate

Figure 3 shows a cyclical component of an exchange rate signal obtained with the HP filter and drawn in the time-frequency domain using two bilinear distributions from the Cohen class. In figures 3a and 3b both Spectrogram and Page distribution are not successful in observing neither the expected period of the cycle nor any other periods that could emerge from the exchange rate patterns. When adjusting the smoothing parameter or the length of the analytical window, figures did not improve period determination.

Figure 3: USD/EUR exchange rate signal using a HP filter.

Figure 4 presents a cyclical component obtained with the median filter. Results in this case improved and the period of a cycle can be determined on different time intervals. In figure 4a Spectrogram shows a period of 181.8 days on time interval $0 < t < 1700$ and a period of 333.3 days on time interval $2000 < t < T$. On figure 4b Page distribution shows a period throughout the whole time interval of 181.8 days. Other energy distribution in this case is negligible.

Figure 4: USD/EUR exchange rate signal using a median filter.

USD/JPY Exchange Rate

Figure 5 shows a cyclical component obtained with HP filter and observed in the time-frequency domain with Spectrogram and Page distribution. In figure 5a when neglecting resolution issues of the Spectrogram, two periods throughout the whole time period can be observed at 64.5 and 90.9 days. When observing

the same signal with the Page distribution in figure 5b, same length of a period in the signal is observed.

Figure 5: USD/JPY exchange rate signal using a HP filter.

In figure 6, when applying the median filter to the original signal, it is expected to obtain similar results as in the case when HP filter is applied to the exchange rate signal. However, both Spectrogram and Page distribution show a period of 333.3 days (see figures 6a and 6b).

Figure 6: USD/JPY exchange rate signal using a median filter.

4.2 Combined signal

Price and volume turnover differentials showed little evidence in obtaining the true combined cyclical component. Same methodological problems were observed in the USD/EUR and USD/JPY exchange rate signals. Extreme value differential in volume data created a signal with a significant jump. All energy

in presence of a high jump is taken as a vertical line, making observation of expected cycles in the time-frequency domain impossible. Inquiry about reasons of significant data differential is beyond the scope of this empirical study.

5 Conclusion

The settlement of an exchange rate at 4 PM in London at the end of the last day of the month sets the base rate for the following month. The exchange rate price is influenced at the end of each quarter and on the last day of the year. External evidence influenced the decision of an exchange rate cycle to be set approximately at 260, 65, and 30 days. The theoretical part of the paper explains basic foundational concepts about time-frequency distributions and with the use of two synthesized signals, shows the expected energy distribution in the time-frequency domain. Two dominated signals forming the SDR structure were selected to observe its periodicity in the time-frequency domain. Firstly, the analysis focused on the cyclical component obtained from the price movement signal. To account for the volume turnover effect, a signal was created using a Laplayer's index. In both compositions, the expected cycles should pair with the theoretical description.

Expected energy distribution in the time-frequency space of a given signal using a bilinear Page distribution should resemble the two theoretically synthesized signals. The synthesized signals are set as a benchmark, whereas creating a synthesized signal on the actual trend would provide additional evidence of the efficacy or accordance of the time-frequency distributions; however, providing additional evidence and setting additional benchmarks was beyond the scope of this discussion. Most signals in the field of economics study variable co-movement [13] or periodicity in the time-frequency domain using wavelet transforms; however, the current inquiry made use of bilinear time-frequency distributions where Spectrogram and Zhao-Atlas-Marks distributions were shown to be most widely used distributions in the analysis of speech signals [16].

Results, to which a property of a length of the period could be prescribed emerged in some cases when observing a cyclical component of the USD/EUR and USD/JPY exchange rate signal in the time-frequency domain. HP filter was not efficient in observing any periods within the signals of the USD/EUR exchange rate. However, median filter with an analytical window length of 250 days, showed a cycle on different time intervals, with the prevailing period of 181.8 days. In the case of USD/JPY signal, application of both filters produced different results. Again, the median filter appeared to be more efficient in observing the period of a cycle in the exchange rate signal. HP filter produced two cycles, one oscillating at 64.5 and the other at 90.9 days. In the case of the median filter, the length of the period was determined at 333.3 days. Cycle periods in the USD/JPY exchange rate pair with theoretical expectations.

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